

CERTIFICATE OF ACHIVEMENT

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

NEW INNOVATION IN NATIONAL EDUCATION

FOR ACTIVELY PARTICIPATING IN THE JOURNAL

Mirzarayimova Zebiniso Mansurbek qizi

FUQAROLARNING MEHNAT HUQUQI. MEHNAT SHARTNOMASI

WILL BE AWARDED FOR THEIR PARTICIPATION IN THE ARTICLE

2023/MAY